

Preparation and Diverse Properties of Cobalt Ferrite Ferrofluid

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Abstract

The synthesis of cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) nanoparticles by sol-gel auto-combustion and their characterization by standard techniques like X-ray diffraction (XRD) used to characterize the structure, the size of the nanoparticles after successful characterization, these magnetic CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles were dispersed in water to obtain ferrite nanofluids i.e. ferrofluids. Poly-vinyl- alcohol was used as surfactant while preparing ferrofluids. In this study, CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel auto-combustion technique. Stable CoFe_2O_4 ferrofluids in various volume fractions (0.0, 0.5 and 1.0) have been prepared using water as base liquid. Poly-vinyl-alcohol was used to increase the inter particle interactions of surface modified CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles. Specific gravity bottle was used to measure density, Ostwald's viscometer used for viscosity measurements and ultrasonic investigations are done by ultrasonic interferometer at 2 MHz for the ferrofluids at different temperatures.

Keywords: Ferrofluid, Cobalt Ferrite, XRD, Ultrasonic

1. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic nanofluids or ferrofluids colloidal suspensions of nano-magnetic particles in base fluids. They have enormous importance in industrial and biomedical applications due to their tuneable thermophysical properties. They have attracted much attention in the past decades because of their potential applications in automobiles, coolants [1], brake fluids [2], domestic refrigerators [2], solar devices [3,4], cosmetics, drug delivery [5], defect sensors [6], microwave absorber [7], optical filters [8], hyperthermia [9], and sealant [10].

Among the magnetic nanofluids, cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) based magnetic fluids have been widely analysed due to high electromagnetic performance, excellent chemical stability, mechanical hardness, and high cubic magneto-crystalline anisotropy. These properties make it a promising candidate for many applications in commercial electronics such as video, audio tapes, high-density digital recording media [11]. Among the mentioned applications, the hyperthermia treatment has been recognized as very novel and promising, and the efficiency of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles has been clearly established [12]. Also, as

concerning biomedical application, the possibility of using radioactive ^{60}Co to produce enriched ferrofluid unlock a new perspective, as for instance in the targeting of cancer cells using antibody-coated nanoparticles [13]. From the literature it is found that there are only few reports available on the ultrasonic properties of nanofluids [14]. Reports on the magnetic nanofluids [15] prove the tuneable optical, rheological and thermal properties and also show the dependence of ultrasonic velocity on the clustering structure of magnetic fluid. A big deviation of the experimental values of velocity and attenuation from the theoretical predictions is also reported [16]. The fundamental understanding of exact mechanisms responsible for the amazing behaviours of magnetic nanofluids still remains unclear because of the lack of molecular level understanding of the ultrafine particles. This fact demands the systematic studies on the molecular interactions of magnetic nanofluids with respect to the variations in concentration, temperature and the external magnetic fields [17].

This paper is intended to the systematic experimental study on the response of cobalt ferrite magnetic nanofluids to the ultrasonic wave propagation for the basic understanding of how the cobalt ferrite nanoparticles

behave in water and how they interact with each other and also with water. Preparing the stable and homogeneous suspensions of cobalt ferrite magnetic nanofluids and attaining a deeper understanding of particle-fluid, particle-particle interactions as functions of concentration, temperature and magnetic field, are the main concern [18-19].

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Preparation of CoFe_2O_4 nanofluids.

Nano-crystalline powder of CoFe_2O_4 was prepared by sol-gel auto-Combustion method. The Auto-Combustion was completed within a minute, yielding the brown-colour ashes termed as a precursor. It is known that the pure CoFe_2O_4 obtained by the sol-gel method can be formed at 600°C and thoroughly crystallized at temperatures above 600°C [20]. The as-prepared powders of all the samples were heat treated separately at 600°C for 4 h to get the final product. The mixture of CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles and water was vigorously stirred for 10 min by dispersing the nanoparticles in double distilled water (DDW). PVA coated CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles were collected. Surface modified CoFe_2O_4 are easily disperse in distilled water in present work we prepare CoFe_2O_4 - Water nanofluids in 0, 0.5 and 1 volume fraction. Prepared sample is ultrasonicated for two hours [21].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

Fig 1: X-ray diffraction pattern of CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles

Fig. 1 represents X-Ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles recorded at room temperature. XRD pattern shows the reflection (220), (311), (222), (400), (422), (511), (440) and (533). All the reflections belong to cubic spinel structure. The analysis of X-Ray

pattern was done by Powder-X Software. The results of XRD pattern confirmed formation of cubic structure with nanophase. The structural parameter like lattice constant, X-Ray density, etc. calculated from XRD data.

From the most intense (311) peak the average sizes of the particles were found to be 37 nm. The lattice constant of the present CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles is found to be $8.388 \text{ \AA} \pm 0.004 \text{ \AA}$ which is closely agree with reported literature [21]. To confirm nano-crystalline nature of prepared CoFe_2O_4 sample, the crystallite size was calculated using Scherrer's formula [21].

3.2 Magnetization

The magnetic properties were studied by pulse field hysteresis loop technique at room temperature. The CoFe_2O_4 shows good magnetic properties with saturation magnetization 83 emu/g . viscosities of ferrofluids also changes by changing magnetic field externally.

3.3 Density Measurement

Figure 2. Variation of density (ρ) with volume

3.4. Measurement of Viscosity

Figure 3: Relation between Viscosity and temperature with volume fraction.

In the present study, an Ostwald's viscometer which is 10 ml capacity is used for the viscosity measurement of Water- CoFe_2O_4 ferrofluids. The viscosity of the Water-

CoFe₂O₄ ferrofluids can be determined using the relation [24].

3.4 Ultrasonic Velocity

Figure 4: Relation between Ultrasonic Velocity and temperature with volume fraction

In ultrasonic interferometer, a piezoelectric crystal slab (like quartz) with parallel faces develops charges of opposite polarity on their faces when it is strained; such a crystal slab exhibits electrostriction when placed in a region of electric field. The speeds of sound in pure liquids and Water - CoFe₂O₄ ferrofluid were measured using single-crystal variable path ultrasonic interferometer operating at 2 MHz the uncertainty in speed of sound measurements was within the range of ± 0.1 ms⁻¹. The obtained values are presented in fig. 4.

4. CONCLUSION

Cobalt Ferrite ferrofluids of (0, 0.5 and 1) concentrations of Cobalt Ferrite have been synthesized and are found to be stable without any phase separation. Ultrasonic parameters have been measured for 0, 0.5 and 1 concentrations and different temperatures. The results clearly point out the enhancement in particle-particle interaction resulting in the formation of chain like clusters at higher concentrations. Experimental results indicated that density of Cobalt Ferrite ferrofluids increases with increasing volume fractions and viscosity of the ferrofluids is increases with increasing volume fraction and decreasing with temperature. As the temperature range chosen for the study is sufficient to make thermal rupture of the open packed structure of water, it can be confirmed that the changes of the acoustical parameters with temperature variation indicate the predominance of the cohesion of water molecules over the thermal expansion

5. REFERENCES

- [1]. Philip J, Shima PD, Raj B. Nanofluid with tunable thermal properties. *ApplPhysLett* 2008;92:043108.
- [2]. Kao MJ, Lo CH, Tsung TT, Wu YY, Jwo CS, Lin HM. Copper-oxide brake nanofluid manufactured using arc-submerged nanoparticle synthesis system. *J Alloys Compd* 2007;134-435:672-4.
- [3]. Yu W, Xie H. A Review on Nanofluids: Preparation, Stability Mechanisms, and Applications. *J Nanomater* 2012;2012:1-17.
- [4]. Dudda B, Shin D. Effect of nanoparticle dispersion on specific heat capacity of a binary nitrate salt eutectic for concentrated solar power applications. *Int J ThermSci* 2013;69:37-42.
- [5]. Mahian O, Kianifar A, Kalogirou SA, Pop I, Wongwises S. A review of the applications of nanofluids in solar energy. *Int J Heat Mass Transfer* 2013;57:582-94.
- [6]. Yang D, et al. Hydrophilic multi-walled carbon nanotubes decorated with magnetite nanoparticles as lymphatic targeted drug delivery vehicles. *ChemCommun* 2009:4447-9.
- [7]. Mahadik, Manasi M., and Prashant B. Kharat. "Aliphatic Organic Compounds: A Substitute of Ferrite Materials In Isolator For High Frequency Application."
- [8]. Mahendran V, Philip J. Naked eye visualization of defects in ferromagnetic materials and components. *NDT&E Int* 2013;60:100-9
- [9]. Taylor RA, Otanicar T, Rosengarten G. Nanofluid-based optical filter optimization for PV/T systems. *Light SciAppl* 2012;1:1-7.
- [10]. Raj K, Moskowitz R. Commercial applications of Ferrofluids. *J Mag Magn Mater* 1990; 85:233-45.
- [11]. Z. Zi, Y. Sun, X. Zhu, Z. Yang, J. Dai, W. Song, Synthesis and magnetic properties of CoFe₂O₄ ferrite nanoparticles, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 321 (2009) 1251-1255.
- [12]. V. Cabuil, V. Dupuis, D. Talbot, S. Neveu, Ionic magnetic fluid based on cobalt ferrite nanoparticles: influence of hydrothermal treatment on the nanoparticle size, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 323 (2011) 1238-1241.
- [13]. P.C. Morais, V.K. Garg, A.C. Oliveira, L.P. Silva, R.B. Azevedo, A.M.L. Silva, E.C.D. Lima, Synthesis and characterization of size-controlled cobalt-ferrite-based ionic ferrofluids, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 225 (2001) 37-40.
- [14]. D.K. Singh, D.K. Pandey, R.R. Yadav, An ultrasonic characterization of ferrofluid, *Ultrasonics* 49 (2009) 634-637.
- [15]. T. Hornowski, A. Józefczak, M. Łabowski, A. Skumiel, Ultrasonic determination of the particle size

- distribution in water-based, magnetic liquid, *Ultrasonics* 48 (2008) 594–597.
- [16]. P. Sayan, J. Ulrich, The effect of particle size and suspension density on the measurement of ultrasonic velocity in aqueous solutions, *Chem. Eng. Process.* 41 (2002) 281–287.
- [17]. M. Motozawa, Y. Iizuka, T. Sawada, Experimental measurements of ultrasonic propagation velocity and attenuation in a magnetic fluid, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter.* 20 (2008). pp. 204117-1–204117-5
- [18]. A. Skumiel, T. Hornowski, A. Józefczak, Investigation of magnetic fluids by ultrasonic and magnetic methods, *Ultrasonics* 38 (2000) 864–867.
- [19]. H.W. Muller, Y. Jiang, M. Liu, Sound damping in ferrofluids: magnetically enhanced compressional viscosity, *Phys. Rev. E* 67 (2003). pp. 031201-1–031201-5
- [20]. 20. Kale, G. H., Humbe, A. V., Kharat, P. B., Bhoyar, D. N., & Jadhav, K. M. Tartaric Acid a Novel Fuel Approach: Synthesis and Characterization of CoFe₂O₄ Nano Particles.
- [21]. A.B. Salunkhe et al, Polyvinyl alcohol functionalized cobalt ferrite nanoparticles for biomedical applications, *Applied Surface Science* 264 (2013) 598– 604
- [22]. Karthikeyan, N. (2015). Ultrasonic Analysis on Molecular Interaction Studies in Liquids and Structural Characterization of Borate Glass Specimen.
- [23]. Dean, J. A. (1990). Lange's handbook of chemistry. Material and manufacturing process, 5(4), 687-688.
- [24]. KirandeepKaur et al, Ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity studies of the binary mixtures of ethyl acetate with hexane, *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2016, 8(7):49-53
- [25]. M. NabeelRashin, J. Hemalatha, Magnetic and ultrasonic studies on stable cobalt ferrite magnetic nanofluid, *Ultrasonics* 54 (2014) 834–840.